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RESTORATION OF HISTORIC CITIES

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Annotation: The first step can be achieved by continuing work on the construction of neighborhood centers as an experiment on the basis of the presented model, and then by practical implementation on the basis of Uzbekistan to create modern neighborhood centers that have been formed for many centuries and serve the rapid development of national traditions.

Keywords: neighborhood, Urban Planning, Samarkand, Center.

The architectural and compositional solution of the modern neighborhood center goes in two ways of re-creation: firstly, the historically formed khajmiy-spatial frames of the Neighborhood Center; secondly, the organization of traditional architectural-artistic.

The historically formed architectural elements of the architecture of the neighborhood centers show so many aspects of themselves that are bright and give pleasure to life that the use of recycled in modern construction practice is successful. Using ancient architecture-images and structures, the use of closures is clearly manifested in the quality of the dome, layers, the sequence of berk walls, the active application of wooden materials (column, door, ceiling). In this case, it is necessary to take into account the relationship between construction and decor:

a) display of the structure using decor and artistic styles;

b) display of decor using a constructive solution;

C) construction-decor, decor-construction mutually complement each other in the artistic-aesthetic plan [34].

A new approach to improving the methodology for designing the architecture of Neighborhood Centers in the city of Samarkand is associated with how correctly the problems associated with the solution of economic factors of objects are identified. In this context, it should be noted that the sheep should be a

means of improving urban planning methodology:

* choosing an area for building a Neighborhood Center;

* effective use of landscape made up of territory;

* the choice of a more optimal solution in terms of Jipping and reproduction of Neighborhood Centers.

The selected area should be located on the territory with sufficient aeration of the territory, the convenience of keeping the structures from sunlight, which allows you to create the required microclimate. High relief Jos are usually chosen for Neighborhood Centers. If there are no such places, it is required to create them artificially. This one-way determines the dominance of the Neighborhood Center in general construction. The placement of the Neighborhood Center on land with greenery and water bodies serves not only to improve the microclimate, but is also the main means of architectural and spatial composition in small neighborhood centers and the entire urban planning environment [26].

New approaches to the cipsization and reproduction of the above-mentioned center facilities lead to a high-level solution of urban planning issues without additional re-Project research. These are the most optimal forms of functional organization of historical neighborhood centers directly related to the cipsization of structures, traced to the traditional methods of urban planning solution.

The first option offered can be used in traditional centers without modifications, so it follows the jipsization of the center's facilities. Each service element here is placed in the category of mutually insulated organizations as a spa, a separate structure. This situation can add objects to the microansable category in the gradual hierarchical formation of the Neighborhood Center. It can embody elements of everyday service.

With the help of the proposed second and third options, it is possible to solve the problem of the functional use of the Neighborhood

Center in a mutually exclusive way. Here, due to the large size of the neighborhood center, there are huge opportunities for expanding the area, the use of traditional service provision elements formed, which meet the forms and requirements of the socio-public and domestic sphere. In the proposed option, it is possible to jipsize at the expense of the addition and intervention of some offices. In this case, it is implied that in the first case the structures are moved by multiplying around the formed one-team area, in the second case by multiplying and moving around several-team areas.

Figure 1. Neighborhood Center

In the proposed drawing, the issue of the principle of Jipping of the neighborhood center facilities as necessary and as far as possible will be corrected (photo – ?). This drawing marks the structures in a single harester for all of the above variants. The proposed principles will increase the cost of rational use of the urban area, increasing the speed on its basis, and most importantly, the provision of services of the Neighborhood Center, which in turn will increase the social and economic efficiency of the Neighborhood Center, which means that it will find a solution to the goal of scientific research.

The principles and recommendations proposed as a result of scientific research for

reconstruction and new projects of neighborhood centers are concentrated in a single generalized theoretical model of proposals and recommendations in drawing and table layout. The model does not bypass all types of architectural-planned and functional organization of the center of the modern neighborhood. In the development of society, new forms of their organization Arise. However, all the factors associated with the provision of traditional social, household services should serve as the basis of the formation, despite all the changes in the life environment. All this was concentrated on the territory of Uzbekistan for many centuries and was considered the main architectural and functional national values in the formation of the architecture of Neighborhood Centers.

1. Public centers embody a unique national urban planning formation that dates back to ancient times, and Historical Cities of Uzbekistan, such as Samarkand, embody a complete and bright image from the neighborhood centers.

2. Neighborhood centers reflect the social economic traditions of the "residential – neighborhood – city" system in the formation of Uzbek urban planning, which has become the primary public link.

3. The system of universal public relations, economic life and aesthetic views are observed in neighborhood centers, especially in the structure of structures, in their proportions, in the artistic solution of the elements of the ensemble.

4. By the 19th century, on the basis of multi-centuries of development, closely related structures within the neighborhood centers were: machites (the main structure with a wide porch, designed for non-public reading), a teahouse (the place of gathering, which continues to rest and Chauffeur), a tower (the place of prayer for people), khanako (the place of residence of representatives of, howitzer (an artificial reservoir designed to store drinking water, and also serves to control the microclimate), greenery (a means by which an artistic composition is attached to the ensemble and creates a favorable bio-climate and aesthetic environment)

5. Three types of neighborhood centers have been formed that meet different urban planning requirements:

- closed neighborhood centers, located in a dense settlement of residential areas in the city, on the roadside of the street, the buildings are grouped around the center courtyard in a holistic planned environment, forming public corridors.

- semi-closed neighborhood centers, the city is located at an average density of residential areas, at the intersection of streets in the form of a square, in which the central building

groups, forming public corridors in a semi-open planned environment around the street.

- * open neighborhood centers, residential areas are combined with public corridors of random shape, adjacent to the central building, regardless of the location of neither the street nor the Square in densely populated areas, places with a free environment.

6. Each structure performs its own specific function in the composition. The composition center is a machit building with a complex prosaic and decorative solution. The field environment is enhanced by Howl, tower and boulders. Secondary facilities-tea house, cells, tolar (Vine). The composition is placed in harmony in proportion to the urban environment.

7. In the area of neighborhood centers, two problems are formed in modern national urban planning: firstly, the regeneration of Neighborhood Centers in the historical urban environment; secondly, the creation of small public centers in the construction of new residential areas. In both cases, the establishment of a new social community, the re-composed an'navi collective life requires the classification of structures within the neighborhood centers:

- kichichich, or micromarkets, as part of – neighborhood committee, Women's committee, nuraniyar Committee, farm buildings, Youth Center, Press Association, teahouse with bakery and somsahan, sports and Wellness Zone (sports grounds), public corridors and greenery for recreation and hrdiq release;

- large, or macromarcas, containing – neighborhood committee, Women's committee, nuraniyar committee, homeowner's company, postal and Communication Service, Youth Center, not too large memorial section, library with exhibition hall and dining room, Press Association, teahouse with bakery and somsahan, food and transverse necessities shop, household service provision, sidewalk buildings, Medical Services Department, Gym,

Sports Ground, public health facilities and greenery for recreation and hrdiq release.

8. In the residential areas formed, the historical neighborhood requires that the regeneration of the Centers reorient the function of the structures, their restoration, adaptation to New needs, the introduction of the necessary additions based on the classification of the composition of individual centers and their structures.

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